

Endogenizing demographic developments in integrated assessment models: a study of global population dynamics under climate change-induced economic degrowth

Abstract

We integrate a regionalized world population model into an integrated assessment model to simulate demographic dynamics until 2100 in four socio-economic scenarios that differ with regard to the presence of population policies and climate change damages to economic production. While world population peaks and declines between 2050 and 2070 in all scenarios, simulations show that both a fertility policy and climate change damages lead to a lower average age of the population and increase the number of births. In scenarios with climate change damages, the size of the world population falls faster due to a strong increase in deaths resulting from a climate change-induced and unintentional degrowth in global economic output. Although all world regions are affected, middle- and low-income countries are hit hardest, as the global convergence in mortality rates observable in the no-climate-change scenario comes to a halt and regional differences in mortality rates increase again. Simulations show that the mortality rate at the regional level in 2100 increases between 1.45- and 3.88-fold compared to scenarios without climate change, with additional deaths per year between 2070 and 2100 ranging from 0.1–1.4 million in high-income countries, 3–12 million in upper-middle-income countries, and 10–22 million in lower-middle- and low-income countries. Our simulations further indicate that a fertility policy in high-income countries, under scenarios with climate change damages, can have adverse effects on mortality rates during the phase of economic decline by lowering consumption levels across all world regions.

Keywords

System dynamics; integrated assessment modeling; world population model; climate damages; global population dynamics; socio-economic scenarios

1. Introduction

Population dynamics are central to the study of global environmental and climate change, as demographic changes both drive and are driven by changing planetary conditions (Muttarak, 2021). Yet, future demographic developments and their interactions with global economic and environmental systems remain inherently uncertain. In this context, multidimensional integrated models provide a systematic and quantitative means of addressing the demography–economy–climate nexus and conducting scenario analyses that can inform policy-making across demographic, economic, and environmental domains.

Models have been used to examine how demographic developments contribute to environmental pressure and climate change by influencing economic growth rates and greenhouse gas emission pathways (Dodson et al., 2020; Kc & Lutz, 2014). At the same time, the size and structural composition of the world’s population—including educational levels and geographic distribution—determine how many people will face the socio-economic impacts of environmental degradation and shape societies’ capacity for both mitigation of and adaptation to climate change (Lutz, 2017; Lutz & Striessnig, 2015).

A second strand of modeling research investigates how adverse climate change impacts may, in turn, affect demographic dynamics. This research direction resonates with scholarly calls to examine catastrophic climate scenarios (Kemp et al., 2022), and with the emerging field of the ‘demography of disaster’ (Karácsonyi et al., 2021). Quantitative studies have addressed a broad range of issues, including the direct impacts of climate change on mortality through various channels such as heat, malaria, dengue, diarrhoeal disease, and undernutrition under different RCP scenarios (Pottier et al., 2021); the temperature-related mortality burden under alternative climate and population scenarios (Hajat et al., 2023; Ignjačević et al., 2024; Rai et al., 2019); and changes in temperature-related mortality burdens with adaptation under different shared socio-economic pathways (SSPs) (Wan et al., 2024). Other studies have explored demographic shifts resulting from flooding (Shu et al., 2023) and the demographic implications of climate-induced migration (Hauer et al., 2024).

Nevertheless, models that simultaneously examine the effects of population on the climate system and of climate change on demographic processes remain scarce. Notable exceptions include the integrated climate–economy–demography models developed by Gerlagh et al. (2023), and by Lupi & Marsiglio (2021), the latter based on the Integrated Assessment Model (IAM) DICE. However, both are limited by their level of aggregation, which prevents them from representing demographic changes at the regional level or accounting for the demographic implications of socio-economic inequality. Moreover, although some scholars have explicitly quantified climate-induced changes in fertility rates in developing countries (Casey et al., 2019; Shayegh, 2017), changes in birth rates are often neglected in modeling exercises addressing the demography–economy–climate nexus (Grace, 2017).

In light of these gaps, the present article pursues three main objectives. First, we aim to illustrate how the interlinked evolution of world population, global economic production, and planetary environmental conditions can be endogenized by coupling a population model with an IAM. Compared to other demographic models that can be integrated into an IAM (Court & McIsaac, 2020; Rozell, 2017), the population model developed here features a higher level of complexity by incorporating disaggregation by region, age, and socio-economic class. Second, we want to analyze how demographic variables at the regional and the global level might evolve in the absence of any global environmental changes, as well as in the presence of population policies.

Last, we explore how climate change might indirectly impact demographic developments through climate-change induced losses in economic production.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. The next section describes the structure of the developed population model and its integration into the selected IAM. We then present the results of four simulation scenarios, highlighting unexpected findings and feedback dynamics. Finally, we discuss caveats in interpreting the simulation results, summarize the key methodological advances resulting from this modeling exercise, and outline avenues for future research.

2. Methods

2.1. A regionalized world population model

We used the system dynamics software Vensim to develop a global scale population model that serves to simulate demographic dynamics over time. For this purpose, the world population is disaggregated into three world regions—center, semiperiphery, and periphery—and into 20 age cohorts in five-year intervals, ranging from the group of zero to four-year-olds to the group of those aged at 95 or older. Thus, each age cohort, except the last, covers five years. The model distinguishes between individuals fully integrated into the global economy and those who subsist partially or entirely at the margin of it. The latter are assumed to derive their means of livelihood primarily from non-monetized sources outside the world economy. Additionally, while all people living in subsistence conditions belong to the same ‘subsistence’ class, the population that lives fully integrated in the global economy is divided into nine consumption classes. The size of the classes is derived by dividing the population at the regional level into the richest 20% (R20), the poorest 30% (P30) and the middle class which covers the remaining half of the population (M50) at every moment of the simulation.

To calculate the evolution of the population fully integrated into the global economy, the following factors are considered: the initial population stock broken down by age and region; the flow of births; the flow of deaths; the flow of population transitioning from the global economy to the subsistence regime; the flow of population moving from subsistence to the global economy; and the population shifting from one age group to another.

The population stock of the youngest age group (zero- to four-year-olds) is calculated according to equation (1), the population stock of the oldest age group (95 or older) according to (2), and the stock of the remaining age groups according to equation (3). A list of subscripts and superscripts is provided in the Appendix.

$$P_{r,c04}^{we} = \int_{t_0}^t \left(B_r^{we} - D_{r,c04}^{we} + M_{r,c04}^{sub2we} - M_{r,c04}^{we2sub} - \frac{P_{r,c04}^{we}}{5} \right) dt + P_{r,c04}^{we}(t_0) \quad (1)$$

$$P_{r,c95+}^{we} = \int_{t_0}^t \left(\frac{P_{r,c9094}^{we}}{5} - D_{r,c95+}^{we} + M_{r,c95+}^{sub2we} - M_{r,c95+}^{we2sub} \right) dt + P_{r,c95+}^{we}(t_0) \quad (2)$$

$$P_{r,am}^{we} = \int_{t_0}^t \left(\frac{P_{r,ay}^{we}}{5} - D_{r,am}^{we} + M_{r,am}^{sub2we} - M_{r,am}^{we2sub} - \frac{P_{r,am}^{we}}{5} \right) dt + P_{r,am}^{we}(t_0) \quad (3)$$

Population dynamics in the model are determined by birth and death flows.

The birth flow is calculated with the population stock and the birth rate of every age group that belongs to the reproductive age, i.e. all age groups between 15 and 44. Birth rates are

endogenously calculated based on per capita consumption ($Cpc_{r,cl}$), which differs between the 9 social classes, and public education expenses per capita ($Edpc_r$). Different functional forms are used to estimate birth rates across age groups to achieve a better statistical fit. When per capita consumption falls below the subsistence level which is constituted by the extreme poverty line of the Worldbank for 2017, a different function is applied to calculate the birth rate. This function is adopted for all age cohorts, and its parameters are adjusted so that when per capita consumption drops to half of the subsistence level, the birth rate drops to zero. If the per capita consumption of a class in the global economy is higher than the subsistence consumption, the birth rates over five years for every age group belonging to the reproductive age are calculated with equations (4) to (9), otherwise they are calculated according to equation (10). Annual birth rates are calculated by equation (11) and the number of births at the regional level is derived by summing over all age groups (12).

$$Br5y_{r,c1519}^{we} = \sum_{cl} \left(\left(yf_{c1519}^{Br5y} + (y0_{c1519}^{Br5y} - yf_{c1519}^{Br5y}) \cdot e^{-\alpha_{c1519}^{Br5y} \cdot (Cpc_{r,cl}^{we,s} + Edpc_r)} \right) \cdot clsh_{cl} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$Br5y_{r,c2024}^{we} = \sum_{cl} \left(\left(yf_{c2024}^{Br5y} + (y0_{c2024}^{Br5y} - yf_{c2024}^{Br5y}) \cdot e^{-\alpha_{c2024}^{Br5y} \cdot (Cpc_{r,cl}^{we,s} + Edpc_r)} \right) \cdot clsh_{cl} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$Br5y_{r,c2529}^{we} = \sum_{cl} \left(\left(yf_{c2529}^{Br5y} + (y0_{c2529}^{Br5y} - yf_{c2529}^{Br5y}) \cdot e^{-\alpha_{c2529}^{Br5y} \cdot (Cpc_{r,cl}^{we,s} + Edpc_r)} \right) \cdot clsh_{cl} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$Br5y_{r,c3034}^{we} = \sum_{cl} \left(\left(\beta1_{c3034}^{Br5y} + \beta2_{c3034}^{Br5y} \cdot \ln(Cpc_{r,cl}^{we,s} + Edpc_r) \right) \cdot clsh_{cl} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$Br5y_{r,c3539}^{we} = \sum_{cl} \left(\left(\beta1_{c3539}^{Br5y} + \beta2_{c3539}^{Br5y} \cdot (Cpc_{r,cl}^{we,s} + Edpc_r) \right) \cdot clsh_{cl} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$Br5y_{r,c4044}^{we} = \sum_{cl} \left(\left(yf_{c4044}^{Br5y} + (y0_{c4044}^{Br5y} - yf_{c4044}^{Br5y}) \cdot e^{-\alpha_{c4044}^{Br5y} \cdot (Cpc_{r,cl}^{we,s} + Edpc_r)} \right) \cdot clsh_{cl} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$Br5y_{r,a}^{we} = \max \left(0, \sum_{cl} \left((\beta0_a^{Br5y} + \beta1_a^{Br5y} \cdot Cpc_{r,cl}^{we,s}) \cdot clsh_{cl} \right) \right) \quad (10)$$

$$Br_{r,a}^{we} = \frac{Br5y_{r,a}^{we}}{5} \quad (11)$$

$$B_r^{we} = \sum_a (p_{r,a}^{we} \cdot Br_{r,a}^{we}) \quad (12)$$

Deaths are calculated from the population stock of different age groups and their respective mortality rates. These mortality rates depend on class-specific per capita consumption and public healthcare expenses per capita (Hpc_r). Death rates over five years are obtained through equation (13), annual death rates through equation (15) and total deaths per year through equation (16). When the per capita consumption of a class belonging to the global economy falls below the subsistence level, a different equation is used (14), which sets the annual mortality rate to 1 once per capita consumption has dropped to half of the subsistence consumption level, reflecting rapidly increasing mortality rates once extreme poverty can no longer be buffered by subsistence-based coping mechanisms.

$$Dr5y_{r,a}^{we} = \sum_{cl} \left(\left(yf_a^{Dr5y} + (y0_a^{Dr5y} - yf_a^{Dr5y}) \cdot e^{-\alpha_a^{Dr5y} \cdot (Cpc_{r,cl}^{we,s} + Hpc_r)} \right) \cdot clsh_{cl} \right) \quad (13)$$

$$Dr5y_{r,a}^{we} = \min \left(5, \sum_{cl} \left((\beta 0_a^{Dr5y} + \beta 1_a^{Dr5y} \cdot Cpc_{r,cl}^{we,s}) \cdot clsh_{cl} \right) \right) \quad (14)$$

$$Dr_{r,a}^{we} = \frac{Dr5y_{r,a}^{we}}{5} \quad (15)$$

$$D_{r,a}^{we} = P_{r,a}^{we} \cdot Dr_{r,a}^{we} \quad (16)$$

To calculate the population flow from the global economy to the subsistence economy, first the share of the population that wishes to migrate is calculated for each region and social class. The share is then used to determine the flow (19). The share is calculated based on per capita consumption and always ranges between 0 and 0.1 (17). The migration flow can be constrained by the amount of land available for subsistence agriculture which depends on the land productivity in the subsistence economy (18).

$$Mr_{r,cl}^{we2sub} = \max \left(0; \min \left(0.1, \beta 0 - \beta 1 \cdot Cpc_{r,cl}^{we,s} (ts - 1) \right) \right) \quad (17)$$

$$MaxP^{sub} = Lnd^s \cdot Int_{sub_lnd}^{Lnd} \quad (18)$$

$$M_{r,a}^{we2sub} = \max \left(0; \min \left(1; \frac{MaxP^{sub} - P^{sub}}{\sum (Mr_{r,cl}^{we2sub} \cdot P_{r,a}^{we} \cdot clsh_{cl})} \right) \right) \quad (19)$$

$$\cdot \sum_{cl} (Mr_{r,cl}^{we2sub} \cdot P_{r,a}^{we} \cdot clsh_{cl})$$

Likewise, the flow from the subsistence economy to the global economy is calculated using the share of people wanting to migrate and the stock of population in the subsistence regime. The share is determined based on the per capita consumption in the lower classes of different regions within the global economy and the fixed per capita consumption in the subsistence sector. It is assumed that the willingness to migrate increases with the difference between the consumption of the poorest classes in the global economy and the consumption in the subsistence regime. If there is insufficient land to sustain the subsistence population (18), forced integration into the global economy occurs. This process serves as an adjustment mechanism when subsistence conditions cannot support the existing population.

$$Mr_r^{sub2we} = \max \left(0; \min \left(0.1; \beta 1 \cdot (Cpc_{r,low}^{we,s} - Cpc^{sub}) \right) \right) \quad (20)$$

$$M_{r,a}^{sub2we} = \max \left(Mr_r^{sub2we} \cdot P_{r,a}^{sub}; \left(\frac{\max(0; P^{sub} - MaxP^{sub})}{P^{sub}} \right) \cdot P_{r,a}^{sub} \right) \quad (21)$$

The same equations (1) to (21), which are used for the population integrated into the global economy, are also applied to the subsistence class, with only two differences. First, instead of using the sum of per capita consumption and public education or health expenses to calculate birth and death rates, only the constant per capita subsistence consumption is used because it is assumed that the subsistence class is not covered by the benefits of public expenditures. Second, in the equations used to calculate population changes, migration terms have reversed signs. This is because migration flows from the global economy to subsistence represent an inflow for the subsistence population but an outflow for the global economy's population stock. Conversely, migration from subsistence to the global economy constitutes an outflow for the subsistence population and an inflow for the global economy.

The non-demographic variables in the population module such as per capita consumption, land intensity or public spending constitute exogenous input variables. At the same time, if required for a particular scenario analysis, endogenous demographic developments can be altered by introducing exogeneous variables that can replace or modify endogenous variables such as birth or death rates.

The data for the initial population stock comes from UN population data for 2020 (UN DESA, 2019c) which disaggregates population into countries and into 21 age groups. We aggregated the two oldest age groups, and aggregated countries into three world regions according to average income levels. The world region 'center' includes the high-income countries; the 'semiperiphery' includes the upper-middle income countries and the 'periphery' covers the lower- and low-middle income countries. The size of the subsistence population was set to 800 million in 2019 of which 85% were matched to the periphery and 15% to the semiperiphery. To determine the parameters of equations (4) - (9) and (13), a total of 25 regression models were constructed based on the disaggregated Exiobase3 final demand data on household consumption and public expenditure for health and education (Stadler et al., 2018) and age-specific mortality and fertility rates from the UN (2019b, 2019a), covering the period between 1995 and 2020. To convert household final demand into consumption per capita, the disaggregated Exiobase3 data was divided by the population size of the respective countries or world regions by using UN population data (2019c). Unlike Court & McIsaac (2020) we do not use gross world output or GDP as independent variable since we hold that only consumption goods, especially education and health services, can have an effect on mortality and fertility rates by changing living standards, while non-consumption goods might be necessary to sustain production processes but do not have a direct effect on demographic variables. While consumption per capita is the most important determinant of fertility and mortality rates we find that the statistical fit can be increased by factoring in per capita public expenses for health in the case of mortality rates, and for education in the case of birth rates. The parameters for equations (4) - (7), (9) and (13) were calculated with nonlinear least squares asymptotic regression models via the R NLS/SSasymp commands from the stats package while the parameters for equations (7) and (8) were estimated by using a logarithmic, and a linear regression model, respectively. Further information on the estimation of model parameters is provided in Lauer & Llases (2025).

2.2. Integration into MORDRED

By coupling the population model with a global economic socially and environmentally extended input-output model based on EXIOBASE3 data, we integrate the model into the IAM 'MORDRED' (Model of Resource Distribution and Resilient Economic Development), which is described in detail in Lauer & Llases (2025). This coupling results in the endogenization of a series of demographic, economic and environmental variables.

First, economic developments influence demographic developments through changes in the per capita consumption of the different social classes that lower or increase age-specific mortality and fertility rates in the three world regions. These class-specific changes in consumption are determined by exogenously determined desired growth rates for every class, and by the availability of economic input factors necessary to produce the desired economic output. When the amount of available input factors is insufficient to satisfy total demand an allocation rule is applied that can be set to prioritize the consumption demands of certain classes or to proportionally reduce the consumption of all classes. The main input factors in the economic model are labor, fossil resources, land and intermediate goods. To provide greater flexibility for

model users, the feedback between input factors and economic production can be deactivated—with the exception of intermediate goods—so that the economy can continue to grow even when one or several input factors become scarce.

Second, demographic developments influence economic developments through the input factor 'labor'. The share of the world population that lives outside of the subsistence sector and falls within the working age, which is set to 15 to 64 years, constitutes the global labor force sustaining the world economy. The maximum number of working hours that can be demanded by economic processes depends on the size of the working force, the participation rate and the number of annual hours worked. The size of economic output that can be produced with these working hours depends on specific labor productivities that differ among the 25 sectors of the economic module of MORDRED. The migration from the subsistence sector to the global economy leads to an increase of the working force. Thus, the input factor labor evolves endogenously in the model and is affected by changes in demographic structures in the three world regions.

Last, economic activities in MORDRED produce greenhouse gas emissions that cause the global average temperature to increase. The adverse impacts of climate change are reflected through a series of non-linear damage functions that influence the capital depreciation, output, input requirements of intermediate goods, land intensities of the subsistence and the global economy, labor productivities and hours worked. Thus, integrating the population model into MORDRED allows us to assess demographic effects of climate change through climate change impacts on economic production processes. Rather than calculating direct increases in mortality rates due to heat (Chapman et al., 2022; Gasparrini et al., 2017; Guibert et al., 2024), other extreme weather events (Ebi, 2014), or the spread of vector-borne diseases (Messina et al., 2019), the IAM simulates possible climate change-induced deteriorations in production efficiencies and declines in economic output that in turn affect both fertility and mortality rates.

Figure 1 illustrates the main links resulting from the integration of the population model into MORDRED.

Figure 1: Main links between the demographic and the economic part of MORDRED. (+) signs indicate the increase of a variable leads to an increase in the variable it influences. (-) indicates that the increase of a variable leads to a decrease in the variable it influences.

2.2. Scenario design

We design four simple scenarios to illustrate different demographic dynamics produced by the model. They are called *Baseline* (BL), *Baseline-High fertility* (BL-HF), *Damages* (DM), and *Damages-High fertility* (DM-HF). The scenarios cover the period 2019 to 2100. To reduce the level of complexity in the model simulation, we deactivate the land scarcity feedback in the model for all scenarios, only focusing on feedbacks between the climate, economy, labor and population modules.

The *Baseline* scenario simulates demographic developments in the absence of exogenous population policies and adverse climate change impacts. Economic development is characterized by high energy efficiency gains and reductions in greenhouse gas intensities but also by strong continuous growth of the world economy, with low- and middle-income regions (periphery and semiperiphery) growing faster than high-income regions (center). This results in a medium-emission pathway with moderate global economic convergence.

The BL-HF scenario differs from the BL only in terms of an exogenous population policy which is specified to increase fertility rates of the high-income countries by 20% for a given consumption level. The policy is applied across all age groups in the reproductive age.

Economic growth, energy and greenhouse gas intensities in the *Damages* scenario are parametrized the same way as in the *Baseline* but climate damages in MORDRED are activated that affect the labor and the economy modules.

In the DM-HF scenario the same fertility policy is added as in the BL-HF scenario.

The parametrization of the scenarios is given in Section 1 of the Supplementary Material (SM). For the simulations, we use MORDRED version 1.0.4, which, unlike version 1.0 features endogenously evolving sectorial labor productivities.

3. Results

This section presents the main demographic dynamics emerging from the different scenario simulations and links them to underlying developments in the economic and biophysical system.

3.1. Demographic developments without climate impacts

3.1.1. No population policies

In the Baseline scenario, world population stabilizes between 2050 and 2070 after an initial phase of growth, peaking in 2055 at 8.7 billion people. Thereafter, population declines markedly, reaching 7.79 billion by 2100 — similar to the level at the start of the simulation (Figure 2a). These developments closely resemble the SSP5 projections and show parallels with SSP1 (Kc & Lutz, 2017). Conversely, SSP population projections based on a continuously growing per capita gross world product by Court & McIsaac (2020) do not peak, resulting in a much larger population by century's end.

The early and relatively low population peak results from rapidly increasing affluence across regions and social classes and moderate convergence between them, accelerating fertility decline. This resonates with both SSP1 and SSP5 – scenarios characterized by strong economic growth, low fertility and mortality as well as high education levels (Cuaresma & Lutz, 2015). By 2100, global annual output reaches €1,200 trillion, and world average consumption per capita exceeds €45,000 per year.

Rising consumption among the poorest 30% in the semiperiphery and periphery drives a continuous transition from subsistence to monetized economic activity. As the consumption gap widens, more people seek to enter the global economy, leading to the near disappearance of the subsistence sector by 2100 (Figure 2b). This dynamic reflects the model's assumption of high migratory capacity and a strong absorptive ability of formal economies to integrate new labor. The Baseline scenario thus reflects a storyline imagining a smooth and successful globalization, with the spread and stabilization of industrialized and monetized production throughout the world.

At the regional level (Figure 2c), population in the center declines continuously, falling by 35% between 2020 and 2100. In the semiperiphery, population rises modestly from 2.9 billion in 2019 to 3 billion in 2031, then declines gradually to 2.44 billion in 2100. In the periphery, population grows strongly from 3.6 billion to 4.9 billion in 2070, before falling to 4.56 billion by 2100. Consequently, the periphery's population becomes increasingly dominant: in 2020 it was 12% smaller than the combined population of other regions, but by 2100 it is 40% larger.

The moderate convergence assumed in the Baseline not only drives these demographic patterns but also shifts regional consumption scales. Despite persistent per capita gaps, the periphery's total consumption rises from one fifth of the center's at the start to 1.7 times the center's and 30% more than the semiperiphery's by 2100. Nevertheless, per capita consumption levels in the periphery are still lower than in the other world regions at the end of the simulation.

Birth and death dynamics underlie these trends (Figure 2d and e). Annual births in the periphery peak in 2035—about 35 years before total population peaks. Between 2035 and 2100, births decline steadily in all regions, with a weak convergence tendency. By 2100, annual births have fallen by **37%**, **43%**, and **23%** in the center, semiperiphery, and periphery, respectively. Deaths rise strongly in the periphery due to population growth and aging (Figure 2h), while in the center they rise slightly because of an older age structure. Although deaths increase in absolute terms, the mortality index (relative to initial rates) declines continuously across regions (Figure 2f), falling by over 70% in the semiperiphery and 75% in the periphery, indicating convergence in absolute mortality by 2100.

Consequently, global population grows older: average age rises from <33 years at the start to >43 years by 2100 (Figure 2g). Demographic convergence also takes place (Figure 2h): the center’s average age rises modestly (41 → 44), the semiperiphery’s from 35.5 to 44, and the periphery’s from <28 to 43 years.

Figure 2: Main demographic dynamics of the Baseline scenario. a) World population; b) population living in subsistence; c) population in the center (blue), semiperiphery (red) and periphery (grey); d) annual births by region; e) annual deaths by region; f) mortality index (initial mortality rate in every region = 100; shows relative changes for every region); g) average age of the world population; h) average age by region.

3.1.2. Exogeneous population policies

Given the continuous decline and aging of the population in the center, it is reasonable to explore the effects of a fertility policy aimed at increasing birth rates. At the same time, it is worth emphasizing that in our scenario simulation, the semiperiphery exhibits comparable demographic dynamics from 2040 onwards. In the model, affluence and economic development raise labor productivity, allowing economies to grow despite aging. Thus, pro-natalist policies in high-income countries (BL–HF scenario) would be motivated less by internal stability concerns than by geopolitical factors, particularly in response to the population growth of other regions (Figure 2c).

As a result, world population in the BL–HF scenario grows slightly faster, peaking at 8.8 billion in 2058 (Figure 3a). In the center, the policy significantly slows population decline, yielding 280 million more people in 2100—over one third of the center’s baseline population (Figure 3b). This difference stems from birth and death dynamics: in the baseline, births decline continuously, whereas in BL–HF they stabilize after 2040 and rise slightly in the last three decades of the simulation (Figure 3c). Deaths follow a similar trajectory in both scenarios until 2070, after which they decrease more slowly under BL–HF. (Figure 3c). As a result of the policy, average age in the center peaks at 42.5 years in 2045, then declines below 41 years by 2090.

Figure 3: Demographic changes due to a fertility policy applied in high-income countries in the BL (black) and the BL-HF scenario. a) World population; b) population of the center; c) total births, d) total deaths and e) average age in the center.

3.2. Effects of climate change on demographic developments

The BL and BL–HF scenarios depict demographic change in the absence of environmental shocks. The following sections demonstrate how these trajectories alter when climate damages to the global production system are introduced.

3.2.1. No population policies

In the Damages (DM) scenario, economic losses from rising temperatures accumulate until global output halts in 2066 due to labor shortages. Economic production collapses between 2066–2075, driven by falling labor productivity, lower production, and shrinking consumption,

before stabilizing at a lower output level. These shocks transform demographic trends (Figure 4a to r). The economic collapse causes a sharper population decline than in the BL scenario (red vs. black line in Figure 4a). While subsistence-economy dynamics remain broadly similar (Figure 4b), climate change reduces land productivity and available arable land. Because land feedbacks on production are deactivated in this simulation, subsistence expansion is unconstrained by global economic land demand. Consequently, land-related damages are not reflected in demographic outcomes—rendering the simulation blind to potential forced migration from subsistence to formal sectors. If such climate-driven livelihood losses were considered, migration to the world economy would likely intensify as long as economic opportunities remained higher. Under stronger economic collapse or weaker convergence, migration could reverse, as impoverished groups reintegrate into subsistence regimes outside monetized structures.

Climate change in the DM scenario not only reduces total population faster but also yields a younger global population (Figure 4c). Average age peaks just above 40 years in 2068, then declines to 38.5 by 2100. Regional divergence grows in the final decades: in the center, population decline accelerates, while in the semiperiphery the economic collapse causes a temporary sharp fall that later stabilizes (Figure 4d and e). In the periphery, this process occurs earlier, and by 2100 its population slightly exceeds that in the BL scenario (Figure 4f).

Climate-induced economic disruption decreases births in the center (Figure 4g) but increases them sharply in the other regions (Figure 4h and i). In the periphery, births show a second peak between **2070–2080**, following the first in 2030–2040. This pattern arises from cohort-specific fertility behavior: younger cohorts (15–29 years) exhibit higher fertility under lower consumption, while older groups (30–39 years) have higher fertility with rising consumption. As economic decline reduces consumption, fertility rises in younger cohorts and falls in older ones. In the center, older groups dominate, producing a net fertility decline. In the semiperiphery and periphery, stronger fertility increases among younger cohorts offset the decline among older ones, yielding higher total births (Figures 2 & 3 in the SM).

Deaths rise sharply in all regions, especially the periphery (Figure 4j-l). In the center, deaths in DM exceed BL by 1–1.4 million annually (2070–2080) and 0.1–1 million (2080–2100). In the semiperiphery, excess deaths reach 9–12 million (2070–2080) and 3–9 million (2080–2100); in the periphery, 19–22 million and 10–19 million, respectively.

While deaths and births drive population size, mortality rates can be taken as an indicator of the quality of life of the population (Figure 4m-o). The DM scenario is characterized by an increase in the mortality rate index from 2067 onwards that affects all age cohorts and all regions. In the center, mortality rises 28% above initial levels by 2100; in the semiperiphery, it returns to initial levels after an earlier 55% decline; in the periphery, it drops to 42 by 2067 but rebounds to 93 by 2100. Thus, relative deterioration is strongest in the semiperiphery, but in absolute terms the periphery experiences the greatest mortality increase. Climate damages thus halt and reverse the mortality convergence observed in the Baseline scenario (Section 2 SM).

Population aging also reverses (Figure 4p-r). All regions become younger, though the shift is modest in the center and pronounced elsewhere: in the semiperiphery and the periphery the climate change induced demographic changes are so strong that they result in a peak and subsequent decline of the average age in the DM scenario. In 2100, the average age in the semiperiphery is 39, compared to 44 in the BL. In the periphery, average age declines from 39 in

2067 to 37 in 2100, compared to an increase to 43 in BL. Hence, the reversal of global aging stems mainly from demographic rejuvenation in poorer regions.

Figure 4: Evolution of key demographic variables in the DM (red) and DM-HF (orange) scenario, compared to the BL (black) scenario. a) World population; b) population living in subsistence; c) average age of the world population;

population in the center (d), semiperiphery (e) and periphery (f); annual births in the center (g), semiperiphery (h) and periphery (i); annual deaths in the center (j), semiperiphery (k) and periphery (l); mortality index in the center (m), semiperiphery (n) and periphery (o); average age in the center (p), semiperiphery (q) and periphery (r).

3.2.2. Population policies

Introducing climate damages in a scenario with a population policy applied to the high-income countries produces notable differences in demographic developments relative to the BL and the DM scenario (orange line Figure 4). World population peaks higher but declines faster, and the global average age falls further, reaching 37.9 years by 2100. However, while the change in average age in the center is the effect of the population policy, in the other regions it stems from adverse climate change impacts.

In the center, the policy raises births relative to DM, but climate impacts dampen its effectiveness—births remain below BL–HF levels. Moreover, the combination of higher fertility in the center and climate-related economic stress has unintended consequences for the demographic development in the semiperiphery and periphery: following the global output collapse, both births and deaths in the semiperiphery and periphery increase more than in DM (Figure 4h-l). As births and deaths have opposite effects on population size, these changes are harder to observe if only the total population is considered (Figure 4e and f). However, as illustrated by the mortality rate index, in the presence of a fertility policy in high-income countries, climate change effects lead to a stronger rise of mortality in all regions, with the relative change being especially pronounced in the center. These unexpected dynamics arise from additional consumption demands in the center. The larger population drives faster pre-collapse economic growth, an earlier downturn, and lower per capita consumption. The resulting pressure from sustaining a bigger wealthier population leads to higher mortality across all regions. Hence, under climate stress, a pro-natalist policy in the center not only proves unnecessary for maintaining, provided that labor productivity grows, but also worsens welfare and mortality outcomes during economic contraction.

4. Discussion

It is important to emphasize that the demographic dynamics presented in the previous section depend strongly on the underlying economic and climate scenario assumptions, particularly the exclusion of land-related feedbacks on demographic and economic developments. Adjusting parameters that influence labor productivity or emission intensities can substantially alter the trajectory of economic output and the interactions between the demographic and economic modules in the damage scenarios. Because most scenario parameters are subject to significant uncertainty, the demographic developments described must not be seen as prediction but rather as plausible dynamics under a given socio-economic and biophysical pathway. Nevertheless, the scenarios serve to illustrate the importance of considering interactions between the world population and the global economy in IAMs, given that demographic dynamics constrain, and simultaneously are constrained by, economic developments. Thus, while we acknowledge the deep uncertainty linked to global environmental changes and their interactions with the global socio-economic system (McLeman, 2025), we hold that endogenizing both demographic and economic developments in IAM related studies produces simulations that are ‘less wrong’ than those that exclude any feedback between population, economic production and climate change from the outset.

A previous study linking climate, economic, and demographic dynamics based on the relationship between gross world output per capita and age-specific fertility and mortality rates (Court & McIsaac, 2020), found that a climate-induced economic collapse could trigger higher population growth, yielding a larger and younger population. In contrast, our simulations—built on feedbacks between regionally and socio-economically disaggregated per capita consumption levels and age-dependent fertility and mortality rates—show an accelerated population decline accompanied by a younger average population, as mortality rises faster than birth rates. In MORDRED, climate damages increase the investment required to sustain production, reducing the share of consumption in final demand and total output as global temperature rises. Because it is consumption, not overall production, that determines life expectancy and fertility, models relying on output or income per capita may underestimate the demographic impacts of climate-driven economic contraction. To improve the accuracy of population–economy–climate projections, our findings suggest using consumption rather than income or production as the key driver of demographic change, while also disaggregating population dynamics by region and age.

Compared with the WHO estimate of 250,000 additional annual deaths between 2030 and 2050 (World Health Organization, 2014), the additional deaths projected in our simulations are one to two orders of magnitude higher. This discrepancy arises because the WHO study considers an earlier period, focuses on selected health outcomes, incorporates adaptation, and assumes continued economic growth rather than contraction. Thus, our findings suggest that the threat of climate change to the capacity of the economy to grow or at least to maintain stable productive processes is a currently overlooked and underestimated threat to future mortality rates. Also, although climate change impacts on fertility remain contested (Ahmed et al., 2024) the indirect effects observed in the MORDRED simulations reveal differentiated impacts across age and socio-economic groups, resulting in clear demographic deviations from a no-climate-change scenario. As noted earlier, our approach does not include direct mortality increases from climate effects such as heatwaves or floods. However, given the relatively small number of people affected compared with the large-scale demographic effects of climate-driven economic restructuring, this underestimation of mortality is likely minor.

The regionalized world population model presented here complements existing demographic models designed for IAM integration (Court & McIsaac, 2020; Rozell, 2017). The main advantage of our exploratory scenario approach lies in its integrated character, which allows simultaneous consideration of multiple drivers shaping demographic futures under severe global environmental change. For example, studies have stressed the importance of considering changes in the age structure when projecting climate change effects on demographic developments because elderly people are more vulnerable to climate change impacts such as extreme weather events (Cole et al., 2023; Lee et al., 2018). MORDRED accounts for regional changes in the age distribution, enabling an assessment of evolving vulnerabilities across world regions. Moreover, studies show that climate impacts on health, fertility, and mortality are mediated by socio-economic conditions (Liu-Helmersson et al., 2019; Messina et al., 2019). For instance, the population at risk from malaria is projected to decline by 2050 when economic growth effects are considered (Béguin et al., 2011) and evidence from India indicates falling mortality rates despite more frequent extreme weather events (Ray et al., 2021). MORDRED reflects these insights by treating socio-economic development as the primary determinant of fertility and mortality, and by framing environmental degradation as acting through changes in economic structure. By distinguishing consumption across socio-economic classes and regions,

the model captures differing vulnerability profiles, with low-consumption households disproportionately affected by indirect climate impacts.

Despite these methodological advances, many critical aspects of the population–economy–climate nexus remain beyond MORDRED’s current scope. We highlight three key directions for future work.

First, the model could be extended to represent migration flows between regions, enabling analysis of migration from the periphery to the center as an alternative to fertility policies, and of complex climate-induced migration dynamics. Such movements may result not only from deteriorating economic and environmental conditions but also from adaptation and mitigation measures, social perceptions, and narratives (Daoust & Selby, 2024) as well as non-economic climate damages currently not represented in MORDRED. For example, extreme weather events do not only affect productive processes but also reduce the quality of life due to their negative effects on mental health – including anxiety, depression and PTSD – (Batra & Erbas, 2025; Brown et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2022) and by restricting the mobility of the affected population, particularly elderly people, adolescents, women and low-income groups (Tang et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2025; Yao et al., 2024).

Second, although the model allows for reversals in migration between the formal and subsistence economies, our simulations show no net migration back to the subsistence regime. This is because economic production stabilizes after the climate-induced growth reversal, and proportional consumption reductions across all classes prevent the poorest households from falling below subsistence levels. However, both migration propensity and the distribution of climate-induced economic losses are uncertain and could vary across scenarios. Future work should therefore explore alternative allocation mechanisms, higher migration propensities, and worst-case scenarios involving greater temperature increases and economic losses, to assess whether some pathways could plausibly trigger large-scale population movements from the global economy back to subsistence—a potential signal of radical economic reorganization.

Last, further insights could be gained by taking into account gender- and age-specific effects of climate change impacts (Alonso-Epelde et al., 2024; Prina et al., 2024) as well as to account for geographic differences (Falchetta et al., 2024; IPCC, 2022) and for direct climate change impacts on mortality and fertility rates (Lüthi et al., 2023; McElroy et al., 2022; Pottier et al., 2021).

5. Conclusion

This study integrated a population model into the IAM MORDRED and used scenario analysis to demonstrate the value of endogenizing demographic and economic dynamics in integrated assessment modeling. Our results show that both fertility policies and climate change impacts substantially influence demographic trajectories, and that population policies in one region can interact with global climate damages to produce unintended effects elsewhere due to the interconnected nature of the world economy. In our simulations, both fertility policies and climate impacts lead to a younger global population; however, fertility policies increase total population size, while climate change accelerates population decline. A climate-induced contraction of global economic production, driven by shortages of labor hours, raises both the number of births and deaths globally. The simulations indicate that mortality increases linked to economic collapse are significant: by 2100, mortality rates in the climate damage scenario are 1.45 times higher in the center and up to 3.88 times higher in the periphery compared to the no-climate-change case, corresponding to annual additional deaths of 0.1–1 million in the center

and 10–19 million in the periphery between 2080 and 2100. Future work could extend the demographic model to include interregional migration flows to better capture climate-induced migration, and further differentiate climate impacts by age, gender, and region. Finally, the methodological approach developed for MORDRED could be applied to other IAMs to enhance their ability to represent the coupled evolution of population, economy, and climate under global change.

Appendix

Subscripts and superscripts used in the model equations. The subscripts denote vectors, subvectors or vector elements. The superscripts complete the names of the variables or link parameters to the variables to be calculated.

Subscripts

Abbreviation	Type	Definition
a	Vector	Age cohort
am	Generic element created for the transition of population from one cohort to another	Middle age (generic cohort)
ay	Generic element created for the transition of population from one cohort to another. It is the cohort prior to the middle-aged cohort	Young age (generic cohort)
c04	Element (inside vector age cohort)	Cohort 0 to 4 years
c1519	Element (inside vector age cohort)	Cohort 15 to 19 years
c2024	Element (inside vector age cohort)	Cohort 20 to 24 years
c2529	Element (inside vector age cohort)	Cohort 25 to 29 years
c3034	Element (inside vector age cohort)	Cohort 30 to 34 years
c3539	Element (inside vector age cohort)	Cohort 35 to 39 years
c9094	Element (inside vector age cohort)	Cohort 90 to 94 years
c95+	Element (inside vector age cohort)	Cohort 95 years or more
cl	Vector	Class
Lnd	Vector	Land
low	Element (inside vector age class)	Poorest class
r	Vector	Region
sub_lnd	Element (inside vector land)	Land used by the population living in the subsistence sector

Superscripts

Abbreviation	Definition
Br5y	Birth rate per five years
Dr5y	Death rate per five years
s	Supply
sub	Subsistence

sub2we	Subsistence to world economy
we	World economy

References

- Ahmed, K. J., Tan, Y., & Rudd, D. (2024). Exploring the relationship between changes in fertility and disasters: A review of the literature. *Journal of Population Research*, *41*(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12546-023-09324-9>
- Alonso-Epelde, E., García-Muros, X., & González-Eguino, M. (2024). Climate action from a gender perspective: A systematic review of the impact of climate policies on inequality. *Energy Research & Social Science*, *112*, 103511. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2024.103511>
- Batra, M., & Erbas, B. (2025). Extreme Weather, Vulnerable Populations, and Mental Health: The Timely Role of AI Interventions. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *22*(4), 602. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph22040602>
- Béguin, A., Hales, S., Rocklöv, J., Åström, C., Louis, V. R., & Sauerborn, R. (2011). The opposing effects of climate change and socio-economic development on the global distribution of malaria. *Global Environmental Change*, *21*(4), 1209–1214.
- Brown, H. E., Balakrishnan, A. K., Stamps, K. M., Obara, L. M., Witte, S. S., & Winter, S. C. (2025). Experiences of extreme weather and mental health in climate-vulnerable communities: Results from a large-scale survey of women living in informal settlements in Nairobi, Kenya. *BMC Psychology*, *13*(1), 1–11.
- Casey, G., Shayegh, S., Moreno-Cruz, J., Bunzl, M., Galor, O., & Caldeira, K. (2019). The impact of climate change on fertility. *Environmental Research Letters*, *14*(5), 054007.
- Chapman, S., Birch, C. E., Marsham, J. H., Part, C., Hajat, S., Chersich, M. F., Ebi, K. L., Luchters, S., Nakstad, B., & Kovats, S. (2022). Past and projected climate change impacts on heat-related child mortality in Africa. *Environmental Research Letters*, *17*(7), 074028.
- Cole, R., Hajat, S., Murage, P., Heaviside, C., Macintyre, H., Davies, M., & Wilkinson, P. (2023). The contribution of demographic changes to future heat-related health burdens under climate change scenarios. *Environment International*, *173*, 107836.
- Court, V., & McIsaac, F. (2020). A Representation of the World Population Dynamics for Integrated Assessment Models. *Environmental Modeling & Assessment*, *25*, 611–632.
- Cuaresma, J. C., & Lutz, W. (2015). The demography of human development and climate change vulnerability: A projection exercise. *Vienna Yearbook of Population Research*, 241–261.
- Daoust, G., & Selby, J. (2024). Climate change and migration: A review and new framework for analysis. *WIREs Climate Change*, *15*(4), e886. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.886>
- Dodson, J. C., Dérer, P., Cafaro, P., & Götmark, F. (2020). Population growth and climate change: Addressing the overlooked threat multiplier. *Science of The Total Environment*, *748*, 141346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141346>
- Ebi, K. L. (2014). Health in the new scenarios for climate change research. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *11*(1), 30–46.
- Falchetta, G., De Cian, E., Sue Wing, I., & Carr, D. (2024). Global projections of heat exposure of older adults. *Nature Communications*, *15*(1), 3678. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-47197-5>
- Gasparrini, A., Guo, Y., Sera, F., Vicedo-Cabrera, A. M., Huber, V., Tong, S., Coelho, M. de S. Z. S., Saldiva, P. H. N., Lavigne, E., & Correa, P. M. (2017). Projections of temperature-related excess mortality under climate change scenarios. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, *1*(9), e360–e367.

- Gerlagh, R., Lupi, V., & Galeotti, M. (2023). Fertility and climate change. *The Scandinavian Journal of Economics*, 125(1), 208–252. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sjoe.12520>
- Grace, K. (2017). Considering climate in studies of fertility and reproductive health in poor countries. *Nature Climate Change*, 7(7), 479–485. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate3318>
- Guibert, Q., Pincemin, G., & Planchet, F. (2024). Impacts of Climate Change on Mortality: An extrapolation of temperature effects based on time series data in France. *arXiv Preprint arXiv:2406.02054*.
- Hajat, S., Proestos, Y., Araya-Lopez, J.-L., Economou, T., & Lelieveld, J. (2023). Current and future trends in heat-related mortality in the MENA region: A health impact assessment with bias-adjusted statistically downscaled CMIP6 (SSP-based) data and Bayesian inference. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 7(4), e282–e290.
- Hauer, M. E., Jacobs, S. A., & Kulp, S. A. (2024). Climate migration amplifies demographic change and population aging. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 121(3), e2206192119. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2206192119>
- Ignjačević, P., Botzen, W., Estrada, F., Daanen, H., & Lupi, V. (2024). Climate-induced mortality projections in Europe: Estimation and valuation of heat-related deaths. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 111, 104692.
- IPCC. (2022). *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA.
- Karácsonyi, D., Taylor, A., & Bird, D. (2021). *The demography of disasters: Impacts for population and place*. Springer Nature.
- Kc, S., & Lutz, W. (2014). Demographic scenarios by age, sex and education corresponding to the SSP narratives. *Population and Environment*, 35(3), 243–260.
- Kc, S., & Lutz, W. (2017). The human core of the shared socioeconomic pathways: Population scenarios by age, sex and level of education for all countries to 2100. *Global Environmental Change*, 42, 181–192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2014.06.004>
- Kemp, L., Xu, C., Depledge, J., Ebi, K. L., Gibbins, G., Kohler, T. A., Rockström, J., Scheffer, M., Schellnhuber, H. J., & Steffen, W. (2022). Climate Endgame: Exploring catastrophic climate change scenarios. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119(34), e2108146119.
- Lauer, A., & Llases, L. (2025). *MORDRED: Model Of Resource Distribution and Resilient Economic Development. Model Documentation*. GitHub. <https://github.com/Pendracus/MORDRED>
- Lee, J. Y., Kim, E., Lee, W.-S., Chae, Y., & Kim, H. (2018). Projection of Future Mortality Due to Temperature and Population Changes under Representative Concentration Pathways and Shared Socioeconomic Pathways. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(4), 822. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15040822>
- Liu-Helmersson, J., Brännström, Å., Sewe, M. O., Semenza, J. C., & Rocklöv, J. (2019). Estimating past, present, and future trends in the global distribution and abundance of the arbovirus vector *Aedes aegypti* under climate change scenarios. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 7, 148.
- Lupi, V., & Marsiglio, S. (2021). Population growth and climate change: A dynamic integrated climate-economy-demography model. *Ecological Economics*, 184, 107011.
- Lüthi, S., Fairless, C., Fischer, E. M., Scovronick, N., Ben Armstrong, Coelho, M. D. S. Z. S., Guo, Y. L., Guo, Y., Honda, Y., Huber, V., Kyselý, J., Lavigne, E., Royé, D., Rytí, N., Silva, S., Urban, A., Gasparrini, A., Bresch, D. N., & Vicedo-Cabrera, A. M. (2023). Rapid increase in the risk of

- heat-related mortality. *Nature Communications*, 14(1), 4894.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-40599-x>
- Lutz, W. (2017). How population growth relates to climate change. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114(46), 12103–12105.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1717178114>
- Lutz, W., & Striessnig, E. (2015). Demographic aspects of climate change mitigation and adaptation. *Population Studies*, 69(sup1), S69–S76.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00324728.2014.969929>
- McElroy, S., Ilango, S., Dimitrova, A., Gershunov, A., & Benmarhnia, T. (2022). Extreme heat, preterm birth, and stillbirth: A global analysis across 14 lower-middle income countries. *Environment International*, 158, 106902. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106902>
- McLeman, R. (2025). Coming to Terms with Deep Uncertainty in the Study of Climate-Related Displacement. *Cosmopolitan Civil Societies: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 17(1), 14–34.
<https://doi.org/10.5130/ccs.v17.i1.9383>
- Messina, J. P., Brady, O. J., Golding, N., Kraemer, M. U., Wint, G. W., Ray, S. E., Pigott, D. M., Shearer, F. M., Johnson, K., & Earl, L. (2019). The current and future global distribution and population at risk of dengue. *Nature Microbiology*, 4(9), 1508–1515.
- Muttarak, R. (2021). Demographic perspectives in research on global environmental change. *Population Studies*, 75(sup1), 77–104.
- Pottier, A., Fleurbaey, M., Méjean, A., & Zuber, S. (2021). Climate change and population: An assessment of mortality due to health impacts. *Ecological Economics*, 183, 106967.
- Prina, M., Khan, N., Akhter Khan, S., Caicedo, J. C., Peycheva, A., Seo, V., Xue, S., & Sadana, R. (2024). Climate change and healthy ageing: An assessment of the impact of climate hazards on older people. *Journal of Global Health*, 14, 04101.
<https://doi.org/10.7189/jogh.14.04101>
- Rai, M., Breitner, S., Wolf, K., Peters, A., Schneider, A., & Chen, K. (2019). Impact of climate and population change on temperature-related mortality burden in Bavaria, Germany. *Environmental Research Letters*, 14(12), 124080. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab5ca6>
- Ray, K., Giri, R. K., Ray, S. S., Dimri, A. P., & Rajeevan, M. (2021). An assessment of long-term changes in mortalities due to extreme weather events in India: A study of 50 years' data, 1970–2019. *Weather and Climate Extremes*, 32, 100315.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wace.2021.100315>
- Rozell, D. (2017). Using population projections in climate change analysis. *Climatic Change*, 142(3–4), 521–529. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-017-1968-2>
- Shayegh, S. (2017). Outward migration may alter population dynamics and income inequality. *Nature Climate Change*, 7(11), 828–832. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate3420>
- Shu, E. G., Porter, J. R., Hauer, M. E., Sandoval Olascoaga, S., Gourevitch, J., Wilson, B., Pope, M., Melecio-Vazquez, D., & Kearns, E. (2023). Integrating climate change induced flood risk into future population projections. *Nature Communications*, 14(1), 7870.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-43493-8>
- Stadler, K., Wood, R., Bulavskaya, T., Södersten, C., Simas, M., Schmidt, S., Usubiaga, A., Acosta-Fernández, J., Kuenen, J., Bruckner, M., Giljum, S., Lutter, S., Merciai, S., Schmidt, J. H., Theurl, M. C., Plutzar, C., Kastner, T., Eisenmenger, N., Erb, K., ... Tukker, A. (2018). EXIOBASE 3: Developing a Time Series of Detailed Environmentally Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output Tables. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 22(3), 502–515.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12715>

- Tang, J., Zhao, P., Gong, Z., Zhao, H., Huang, F., Li, J., Chen, Z., Yu, L., & Chen, J. (2023). Resilience patterns of human mobility in response to extreme urban floods. *National Science Review*, 10(8), nwad097. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nsr/nwad097>
- UN DESA. (2019a). *World Population Prospects 2019, Online Edition. Rev. 1. File FERT/7: Age-specific fertility rates by region, subregion and country, 1950-2100 (births per 1,000 women)*, WPP2019_FERT_F07_AGE_SPECIFIC_FERTILITY.xlsx. This data gives age-specific fertility rates for 7 age categories (15-19, 20-24, ..., 45-49).
- UN DESA. (2019b). *World Population Prospects 2019, Online Edition. Rev. 1. File MORT/4-1: Deaths (both sexes combined) by five-year age group, region, subregion and country, 1950-2100 (thousands)*, WPP2019_MORT_F04_1_DEATHS_BY_AGE_BOTH_SEXES.xlsx.
- UN DESA. (2019c). *World Population Prospects 2019, Online Edition. Rev. 1. File POP/7-1: Total population (both sexes combined) by five-year age group, region, subregion and country, 1950-2100 (thousands)*.
- Wan, K., Hajat, S., Doherty, R. M., & Feng, Z. (2024). Integrating Shared Socioeconomic Pathway-informed adaptation into temperature-related mortality projections under climate change. *Environmental Research*, 251, 118731. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2024.118731>
- Wang, Y., Gao, S., & Manini, T. M. (2025). Age-Related Deficits in Mobility Resilience With an Extreme Weather and Climate Event. *JAMA Network Open*, 8(7), e2518525. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2025.18525>
- World Health Organization. (2014). *Quantitative risk assessment of the effects of climate change on selected causes of death, 2030s and 2050s*. World Health Organization.
- Yao, Q., Shan, X., Li, M., & Wang, J. (2024). The Impact of Floods on the Mobility of Automobile Commuters in Shanghai Under Climate Change. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Science*, 15(6), 986–1000. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13753-024-00604-3>
- Zhang, R., Zhang, Y., & Dai, Z. (2022). Impact of Natural Disasters on Mental Health: A Cross-Sectional Study Based on the 2014 China Family Panel Survey. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(5), 2511. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19052511>